

PROGRESS AND PERFORMANCE OF BIO-CONTROL LABORATORY: A PROJECT APPRAISAL

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Introduction

Biological control is one of the integral components of the IPM which involves the use of any living organisms and its by-product to contain other living organisms. Bio-control comprises of natural enemies, and the disease-causing microbes in insect pests viz., bacteria, fungi, viruses and nematodes and their by-products to regulate the insect pest population below economic threshold level.

Despite the promising impacts of bio-pesticides, the Indian bio-pesticide industry is growing at a very slow pace. The bio-pesticides accounted for approximately 0.2 % during 2000 of the total global pesticides market and it increased to 4.5 % by 2010. In India, bio-pesticide production is currently dominated by antagonistic fungi and bacteria such as *Trichoderma* spp. and *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. To contain the insect pests many bio-control agents are effective and they need to be explored and native bio-control agents are highly effective in suppressing the insect pests.

Sub Mission on Plant Protection and Plant Quarantine (SMPPQ)

The Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India performs regulatory, monitoring, surveillance and Human Resource Development functions through a scheme “Sub Mission on Plant Protection and Plant Quarantine” (SMPPQ) which is one of the Schemes under Green Revolution (Krishonnati Yojana), with total central share of Rs.1022.67 crore, which aims to minimize loss to quality and yield of agricultural crops from the ravages of insect pests, diseases, weeds, nematodes, rodents, etc., to shield our agricultural bio-security from the incursions and spread of alien species and to promote good agricultural practices. The SMPPQ has the different components such as Strengthening and Modernization of Pest Management Approach in India (SMPMA), Strengthening and

Modernization of Plant Quarantine Facilities in India (SMPQF), Monitoring of Pesticide Residue at the National Level (MPRNL) and National Institute of Plant Health Management (NIPHM).

Central Integrated Pest Management Centres (CIPMCs)

For strengthening and Modernization of Pest Management Approach in India (SMPMA), the Central Government has established 35 Central Integrated Pest Management Centres (CIPMCs) of Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine & Storage (DPPQ&S) in 29 States and one UT. The mandate of these centres are to monitor insect pests and diseases for forewarning, conservation of natural enemies in farmers' fields, production and field release of bio-control agents, promotion of eco-friendly IPM inputs by imparting training to extension officers and farmers through Farmers Field Schools (FFSs), Seasonal Long Training Programs (SLTPs) or Short duration (2/5 days) IPM programs. Total 3239 numbers of Farmers Field Schools (FFSs) have been organized wherein 97170 farmers were trained. An area of 42.49 lakh have been covered under pest monitoring surveillance and 10286.21 million biocontrol agents have been released on field crops in different states for controlling different pests and diseases. For modernization and strengthening of bio-control laboratory and mass production unit, each CIPMCs is already engaged in production and mass multiplication of bio-control agents viz. *Trichogramma* spp., *Chelonus blackburni*, *Epiricania melanoleuca*, *Chrysoperla* spp. etc. for subsequent release in farmer's fields and for demonstration purpose. However, the number of bio-control agents produced is not sufficient to cover the whole state and for distribution among farmers spread over different locations. Therefore, some additional equipments were procured for Modernization and Strengthening of all CIPMCs Lab for mass production units, so as to facilitate and ensure sufficient number and quality bio-control agents to the farmers.

State Bio-Control Laboratory (SBCL)

In order to promote non chemical intervention to pest management through bio-control agents in different states of India, the department provides financial assistance to the States in form of Grant-in-Aid for establishment and strengthening of State Bio-Control Laboratory (SBCL). For setting up new State Bio Control Lab (SBCL), 80.00 lakh rupees for building and 48.81 lakh rupees for equipments were sanctioned. Currently, there are 38 State Bio-control Laboratories (SBCLs) in different states and UTs of India, established under Grants-in-Aid by Government of India during Xth & XIth Plan.

Fig.1: Some CIPMCs in different states of India

Numbers of Bio-control Laboratories in India

Sl. No.	Type of Lab	Number of Labs
1.	CIPMCs	35
2.	SBCLs (Grant in aid)	38
3.	ICAR	49
4.	SBCL	98
5.	Private	141
	Total	361

Aims and Objectives of bio-control laboratories

The main objective of the bio control laboratory is the mass production of bio agents for control of pest and diseases as they are the integral and indispensable part of Integrated Pest and Disease management. To identify the potential native isolates of bio-control agents, their characterization and development of mass production of potential macrobioagents (parasitoids and predators) and microbioagents (fungi and viruses) of the key pests prevail in their particular region to cater the needs of the farmers, to take up the large scale production of potential biocontrol agents, to supply quality bio-pesticides to the farmers of their respective areas, to train the rural youths on the production of bio-control agents and to create awareness on the use of bio-control agents.

Activities of bio-control laboratories

In research field, refining and developing of mass production technologies of bio-control agents like *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Lecanicilium lecanii* and

Nomuraea rileyi, different species of *Trichogramma*, *Spodoptera litura* NPV, and various studies on compatibility with chemical insecticides with bio-control agents are also carried out based on the needs of each regions. In extension field, transfer of technologies on bio-control by educating farmers as well as extension workers about the bio control agents, organizing periodical training, publishing popular articles, leaflets, T.V and radio talks on bio-control as a part of an important components.

Conclusion

It is strongly believed that farmers would utilize bio-control products, like entomopathogenic bacteria, fungi, and viruses, in addition to different natural enemies, in place of insecticides. The [Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare](#), Govt. of India has also taken various steps in scrutinizing many bio-control missions, implementing central as well as state bio-control laboratories across the country so as to make the bio-control programs a successful one. Therefore, it is important to understand the significance of these products and their environmental safety, to understand the current status and performance of bio-control laboratories in our nation.

References

- Biocontrol Unit, University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur, India, (2020).
<https://uasraichur.karnataka.gov.in>
- [Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare \(2021\)](#), <https://agriwelfare.gov.in>
- Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine and Storage (2020), <https://ppqs.gov.in>
- Press Information Bureau (2019), <https://pib.gov.in>